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UNLEASHING POTENTIAL OF MATERNAL ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN LITHUANIA: CAREER OPPORTUNITIES AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMPETITIVE ADVANTAGES

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ABSTRACT

This is the first scientific paper on maternal entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship dynamics in Lithuania which extensively tackles the challenges, opportunities, and untapped potential of the examined group of entrepreneurs via the triangulation method. The aim of the paper is to examine the perspective and career decision-making process of Lithuanian mothers, while explaining how companies could recognize motherhood-specific values and motives in order to develop organizational competitive advantages. Despite efforts to foster female entrepreneurship, men are more likely to launch new ventures than women, while academic research, governmental support or organizational cultures are insufficient to accelerate the process of female entrepreneurship among single mothers. Maternal entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship are academically underdeveloped topics; thus, the research question how to empower mothers to achieve organizational competitive advantages in Lithuania through entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship is relevant and of significant value-added. The methodology focuses on the combination of quantitative survey (of 359 Lithuanian mothers) and semi-structured interviews (with managers of 8 Lithuanian companies). The research results confirm that mothers seek financial gain and work-life balance within their entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship activities, seeking for corporate social responsibility and work flexibility, which, unfortunately, are insufficiently emphasized by Lithuanian organizations.

KEYWORDS: Maternal Entrepreneurship; Innovation; Intrapreneurship; Work-Life Balance, Career Choices, CSR.

Reference to this paper should be made as follows:

JEL Classification: M14, F23, O15, J16, L26

1. INTRODUCTION

Despite all efforts to foster female entrepreneurship, men are more likely to initiate new entrepreneurship activities than women (Global Entrepreneurship Monitor, 2022). Entrepreneurship is often associated with risk taking and financial success (Ali Ramadhan Bin-Husayn *et al.*, 2025), along with ownership or social, corporate, innovative, high growth business development. The sub-domain term 'Female Entrepreneurship' has been ignored by the academic community for 220 years, since the inception of the term (Meyer, 2018). However, it might be interpreted in the context of cultural and social norms (Ali Ramadhan Bin-Husayn *et al.*, 2025) and social structure of network (Ponzetto & Troiano, 2025). Birth of a child might be associated with maternal entrepreneurship, which requires more flexibility in work-life balance and often leads to the pursuit of new business activities. It might be related to how people think and behave in particular situations (Nijs, 2025). Maternal entrepreneurs can be classified into two groups: low-skilled mothers who are forced to quit their jobs and start their business primarily for financial reasons or high-skilled mothers who choose to quit their jobs and pursue a business for flexibility reasons. Moreover, the term "mompreneurs" is also used to describe housewives who pursue business ventures in search for a better work-life balance (Wijaya & Layman, 2018). According to Casteleijn-Osorno and Hytti (2025), who tackle the liaison between mompreneurship and resilience, to unlock the potential of mompreneurs a supportive institutional framework, such as affordable childcare, is necessary to turn their resilience and networking to diverse tangible entrepreneurship outputs. The second sub-domain term "Female Intrapreneurship" could be described as entrepreneurship within an organization, while intrapreneurship and corporate entrepreneurship are interchangeable terms that describe the initiative to create new products, services, and projects within a corporation (Castro & Elizabeth, 2019).

Both types of entrepreneurship require innovation and are viable alternative career paths for new mothers. Personality characteristics are yet another similarity between female entrepreneurs and intrapreneurs. For decades, the Big-5 test model (covering aspects, such as conscientiousness, extraversion, openness to experience, agreeableness, and neuroticism) has been the most popular tool in identifying personality characteristics that lead to specific behaviours (Feher & Vernon, 2021; Holman & Hughes, 2021). During the Big-5 model analysis

entrepreneurs usually score highest in open to experience and conscientiousness (Kerr *et al.*, 2018); intrapreneurship is also linked to openness and being conscientious (Woo, 2018). In many cases intrapreneurship is just a part of a person's transition from an employee to an entrepreneur. There is no single well-accepted definition of mompreneurship, some researchers include that there must be 50% ownership of a business, or that it must be a home-based business, or that the motivation must stem from mothers' experience during the pregnancy or raising a child (Dhaliwal, 2022). However, all mompreneurship researchers agree that mompreneurs must be women who are driven by the need to have enhanced family life and career. Nowadays, the term mompreneurship is also interpreted as a movement (engaging companies, governments, and associations), focused on the networking aspect which is the most difficult part for mompreneurs in the male-dominated field. These stakeholders will be an essential part of this research paper since they create the context in which modern mother entrepreneurs or intrapreneurs must make their career choices.

The liaison between maternal entrepreneurship and organizational competitive advantages has been substantiated and conceptualized via three angles. The first is related to organizational capabilities to create the culture and work environment (along with HR practices, creativity, innovation, risk management, monitoring, communication, learning ecosystem, financial support, work-life balance, etc.) in favour of maternal intrapreneurship or potential maternal entrepreneurship, as well as efficient engagement of returning employees. If necessary processes, preconditions, and inclusive leadership are implemented (with sufficient OPEX expenditures), this pillar might lead to stronger social image, faster organic growth, lower employee turnover, more efficient use of resources, stronger profit margins (compared to peers), bigger number of commercialized innovative ideas, more efficient differentiation strategies, stakeholder satisfaction, bigger social value-added, and the overall competitive advantage of a company. The second conceptual angle is related to an individual career choice of mother entrepreneurs (when a mother decides to not return to her organization, while diving into an independent nascent business or startup or gradually shifting from the career of an employee to a status of an independent entrepreneur). This pillar is centred on the reshaped individual intentions, motives, aspirations, attitudes, challenges, and new creative ideas. The third

perspective is related to potential collaboration and synergy effects between mother entrepreneurs and former employer, or investment in mother entrepreneurship. It might open many strategic directions and potential growth opportunities for both parties, while the outcomes might be measured by diverse metrics, such as ROI, value-added, opportunity costs, gap indicators, pricing ratios, or synergy effects. The linking axis of three fundamental conceptual pillars should be related to the career choice and motives to become a mother entrepreneur or intrapreneur that should be encouraged by both governmental organizations, employers, and other stakeholders.

Thus, in the context of this research mother-entrepreneurs and intrapreneurs will be defined as mothers who decided to change their career trajectory by pursuing new entrepreneurship opportunities outside or within their workplace. This decision must be influenced by the experience they had during or after the maternity leave. It means that women who have developed their business prior to the birth of their first child will not be included in the definition since their motives, environment, and career pivot decision-making process was different. The newly developed term *momprenuers* in the paper will be used to describe both mother entrepreneurs and intrapreneurs.

Although female entrepreneurship is steadily becoming a normalized concept in today's society, the motherhood aspect and the effects it has on women entrepreneurs remains an underexplored topic (Hudson Breen & Leung, 2020; Henry et al., 2021). Many mothers face barriers to traditional employment, such as inflexible work hours and limited access to childcare. By starting their own businesses or becoming intrapreneurs within a larger organization, mothers can create work arrangements that better fit their needs and the needs of their families. Starting a business or becoming intrapreneurs can provide mothers with the opportunity to generate income and build wealth. In today's economy, many mothers are the primary breadwinners for their families, and entrepreneurship or intrapreneurship can help support their families financially. Additionally, entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship can provide mothers with the opportunity to pursue their passions and interests, which can lead to greater job satisfaction and fulfilment. Moreover, economic factors can also disrupt maternal entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship. For example, starting a business can be risky and costly, and mothers may face financial challenges, such as an inadequate

access to capital and limited financial resources (GEM, 2022). Additionally, the economic environment can be unpredictable and volatile, and mothers may face challenges, such as market competition and changing consumer preferences (Hudson Breen & Leung, 2020). These factors can make it difficult for mothers to succeed as entrepreneurs or intrapreneurs (Casteleijn-Osorno and Hytti, 2025).

Technological factors and innovation also play a role in motivating and disrupting maternal entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship. On the one hand, technological advances can provide mothers with new tools and resources to support their businesses or intrapreneurial endeavours (Toke, 2024). Additionally, advancements in technology have created new markets and opportunities for mothers to innovate and create value (Seet et al., 2022). However, technological factors can also disrupt maternal entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship: the rapid pace of technological change can make it difficult for mothers to keep up and adapt to modern technologies and trends (GEM, 2022). Innovation can provide mothers with new ideas, products, and services to support their businesses or intrapreneurial endeavours, along with the opportunity to create value and differentiation, which can lead to competitive advantages and success in the marketplace (Welsh et al., 2018, Pahuja et al., 2024). The rise of online marketplaces and sharing platforms has disrupted traditional retail and hospitality businesses, and mothers who are entrepreneurs or intrapreneurs in these sectors may face increased competition and uncertainty (GEM, 2022).

To conclude, micro and macro factors play a significant role in motivating and disrupting maternal entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship. Economic factors, such as the need for flexible work arrangements and the potential for financial gain, can motivate mothers to start their own businesses or become intrapreneurs. Nevertheless, economic challenges, such as inadequate access to capital and unpredictable market conditions, can hinder maternal entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship. Technological factors, such as the proliferation of the internet and mobile technologies, can provide mothers with new tools and resources to support their businesses or intrapreneurial opportunities.

Internal and external factors play a significant role in encouraging and disrupting maternal entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship via the psychological, social, and environmental factors. For instance, from the perspective of self-efficacy, which

refers to individuals' belief in their ability to successfully complete a specific task or achieve a specific goal, mothers with high self-efficacy and motivation are more likely to believe in their ability to start and run a successful business or pursue an intrapreneurial venture, as well as being more resilient and persistent in face of challenges and setbacks (Dong et al., 2019), if necessary social support and encouragement are present. However, social factors can also hinder maternal entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship in form of barriers, social isolation, stigmas, and biases, such as gender stereotypes and discrimination, which can limit their opportunities (Welsh et al., 2018).

Environmental factors can also motivate and disrupt maternal entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship; the external environment can provide mothers with opportunities and resources to support their businesses or intrapreneurial activities. Additionally, mothers who are entrepreneurs or intrapreneurs can benefit from supportive policy environments, such as policies that promote entrepreneurship or support small businesses, which can provide access to resources, services, and networks (Hudson Breen & Leung, 2020). On the other hand, mothers may face economic challenges, such as inflation, recession, or market instability, along with regulatory challenges, disrupted supply chains, damaged infrastructure, and effects on health and safety at their work environment. Moreover, the specificity of an industry should be taken into account: mothers-entrepreneurs or intrapreneurs can benefit from industries that offer opportunities, resources, and support, but they can also face challenges and constraints in male-dominated and heavily competitive industries. These industry-specific factors can reshape experiences and outcomes of maternal entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship, and they can influence mothers' motivation, success, and well-being.

To continue, cultural and social norms might have a significant impact on mothers-entrepreneurs. The impact of masculinity versus femininity on maternal entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship can vary across diverse cultures and economies, and it can affect mothers' experiences and outcomes in the workplace. For instances, in feminine cultures, mothers may have more support and recognition for their entrepreneurial or intrapreneurial activities, and they may face fewer barriers and biases (Badghish et al., 2022), while having access to more supportive policies and programs, such as parental leave and flexible work arrangements, along with societal perception towards career choice among

mothers-entrepreneurs (Cullen & Archer Brown, 2020). These factors can facilitate mothers' success as entrepreneurs or intrapreneurs in feminine cultures.

2. THE POWER OF SHIFT: INTRAPRENEURSHIP AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP

Unlike entrepreneurship deriving from individual initiatives, intrapreneurship can be nurtured and is dependent on the organizational environment. Most organizational structures and policies in the modern corporate world indirectly discourage new ideas and sometimes demoralize intrapreneurial employees (Badoiu et al., 2020; Bartholomeusz, 2021). Strategies differ from one organization to another. However, they all should address the shift, related to parenthood, often accompanied by values shifting to tradition, security, and conformity (Lönnqvist et al., 2018). Moreover, diversity and inclusivity leadership are critical to unleash the potential of maternal intrapreneurship, while engaging them in a vast variety of innovation projects and activities (Noor et al., 2024; Bersin, 2024). Based on this shift of values, risk mitigation and support from top management should be implemented for mother intrapreneurs based on their value shift.

Internal organizational factors promoting women's intrapreneurship include dimensions, such as communication, flexibility, network, stakeholders, human-resources. Moreover, happiness might also be linked to higher levels of intrapreneurship, as a consequence of a more informal and positive internal communication with managers (Ravina-Ripoll et al., 2022). Workplace schedule flexibility is yet another characteristic that impacts female empowerment positively; it reduces stress and responsibility conflicts, while reshaping attitudes towards work (Rafique et al., 2022). Internal network is a crucial element which determines whether women initiate innovative ideas: women who have developed close relationships with their co-workers and managers are more likely to show intrapreneurship characteristics (Zhang et al., 2020). Considering that a substantial internal network significantly improves chances of female intrapreneurship, it is crucial to look into mentorship and how it could be coordinated to support mothers. For instance, if a woman employee is paired to a mentor who is an already successful female intrapreneur (compared to female employees with male mentors), she is more likely to undertake innovative initiatives herself (Turro et al., 2020). This phenomenon is also true about choosing a similar career trajectory as one's

mentor. For example, the research conducted in the US Military Academy showed that women who possess a female army mentor are 18% more likely to choose their supervisor's specialization than women who have a male mentor (Kofoed & McGovney, 2019). Taking into account this quantitative analysis, successful mentorship programs that are developed by human-resource (HR) departments are not just helpful in speeding up female employee integration and identifying potential future leaders (Iverson, 2019), but also in improving the levels of female intrapreneurship. Thus, HR departments should aim to find new ways to encourage mentorship among women. The increased female participation in mentorship programs would subsequently improve female intrapreneurship.

Sensitization is another factor that promotes women intrapreneurship and is also mainly dependent on the HR department, covering functions, such as educating and making everyone aware of stereotypes and prejudices against women, along with emotional support systems for employees in their maternity journey (Biju & Pathak, 2020). HR departments should constantly monitor the mental health of women employees throughout the pregnancy and birth of a child and be prepared to offer counselling options as well as treatment to mothers (Wilkinson, 2022). A mental health support system might positively affect the employee turnover among women during or after maternity leave, along with their engagement in diverse initiatives; it will also affect social responsibility effectiveness/efficiency and social image, and it would contribute to attracting more women to open positions. Diverse female intrapreneurship promotion strategies would be worthless if there were no ways to track the results they yielded. Monitoring in the HR department is especially difficult in terms of tracking aspects, such as employee happiness.

Currently, there are just a few intrapreneurship monitoring frameworks, created by scholars (Kaaria, 2024). One of them is called employee intrapreneurship scale (EIS) and it aims to measure employee initiated new product behaviour as well as employee initiated new strategy behaviour (Gawke et al., 2019). However, it is only applicable in an academic research context. Thus, modern organisations should focus on developing a more holistic and business intelligence-based intrapreneurship monitoring methodology that could work out of the box for tracking corporate mompreneurship. The percentage of engaged women and mothers should be also tracked, while gender biases should be efficiently addressed (Chang

& Milkman, 2020). Ultimately, mompreneurship monitoring should be implemented to assess current organizational conditions, followed by identification of internal organizational factors suppressing female intrapreneurship, and lastly, the best industry practices should be applied. Innovative HR strategies supporting mothers might help enhance corporate competitive advantages, if a right strategy, along with actions plans, is implemented and monitored. According to Rua and Santos (2022), competitive advantages are outstanding properties of an organization, compared to peers. Various tactics, such as diversity and inclusion, social responsibility, and productivity should be tackled. Foster's et al.'s (2021) study of DiversityInc's "Top 50 Companies for Diversity" indicates that organizations that invest in diversity management enhancement improve their long-term performance faster (whether it is through financial results, increased shareholder value or greater employee attraction and retention). Inclusion can come in various forms ranging from acceptance of different gender, age, race, nationality, sexual preference, religion, character traits, and many other factors (Servaes et al., 2022).

Paganini's and Gama's (2020) case study (part of a hackathon to encourage female engagement) reveals that within a misogynous technology sector (Bérubé et al., 2024), diverse female engagement programs make women feel more confident; Dyson (2024) adds that modern technologies might help inclusive leadership engage stakeholders. However, performance enhancement requires additional preconditions. Inclusion of women in intrapreneurial teams and decision-making processes is also confirmed by Gama (2020): men dominance examples illustrate a negative impact on women's comfort in group, consequently leading to weaker collective intelligence and poorer results. Thus, diversity does not directly impact team effectiveness, while certain areas, such as R&D, might suffer from insufficient inclusion of diversity representatives in innovation processes (Wong, 2024). For example, looking at Pollok's et al.'s (2021) study of over 5,000 board game design campaigns, it is found that hobbyists or users can outweigh professionals in team effectiveness due to motivation coming from their amusement and engagement in the creation process rather than business rewards, consequently resulting in hobbyists being more creative. If same concept is applied to mothers, it can be seen how they would enrich their teams with creativity and contribute to knowledge diversity especially if a project is related to parenting problems. If there is an intrapreneurial project with respect to helping

mothers, naturally they would be willing to know parenting pain points. Thus, gender equality, as part of CSR, might add bigger value to the organizational performance. Based on the 26 round National Longitudinal Survey of Youth, conducted by Yu and Hara (2021) throughout 1979-2014, the wage gap is still present: mothers are disadvantaged when applying to a new workplace rather than staying in the same organization, whereas fathers gain more externally than internally. In addition, Ward and Lee (2020) found an indirect connection between parental stress and child intellectual development. Furthermore, Taubman-Ben-Ari's et al.'s (2021) study claims that diverse uncertain situations might worsen perception of life. Thus, companies could provide more support to parents during diverse vulnerable times (Kadale et al., 2018) via diverse intrapreneurship initiatives. The improved conditions to raise children in a healthier and less stressful environment would create social value-added and lead to better intrapreneurial ideas (Ghafoor & Haar, 2021).

Possessing innovative human capital as a key axis of a strategy is already a great competitive advantage: while employees, along with their demographic attributes, are valuable to companies. However, due to women being statistically underrepresented in enterprises (Geiger, 2020), it is important to focus on what differentiates mothers and women in terms of both intrapreneurial and entrepreneurial capabilities, as well as what preconditions are necessary to support them. A study by van Wetten et al. (2020) concluded that championing skills (compelling people and accelerating projects) and creativity are major factors for facilitating innovativeness in enterprises. A cross-sectional survey of over 550 students discovered a direct connection between self-identified creativity and entrepreneurial plans or objectives (Laguía et al., 2019). Bhansing et al. (2018) connected creativity to passion for job activities, demonstrating that the feeling of inspiration is positively affected by entrepreneurs' enthusiastic engagement leading to motivation to commercialize creative ideas. Moreover, from the motherhood perspective, during pregnancy mothers discover a lot of new information about infants, start learning new things and extend their knowledge sets. Consequently, they become more creative and capable to combine the new gained and diversified knowledge, while turning it into new entrepreneurial solutions.

Moreover, organizational capabilities are relevant in the context of intrapreneurship due to the need to efficiently schedule various tasks, meetings, and

mental capacity to retain focus, along with resilience. The conditions of raising a child and supplying the family financially may portray adaptiveness, quicker recuperation from incidents, and resilience, which is critical for entrepreneurship (Yulita et al., 2020).

Mothers get to meet many other mothers throughout the course of pregnancy and years of child development that they widely expand their connection circle. Combining this with Bhansing et al.'s (2018) work, entrepreneurial people are positively affected and inspired by other passionate entrepreneurs. It can be projected that if the number of intrapreneur mothers sharing their positive experiences increases this could create a chain reaction of more mothers being attracted to the endorsed organization and motivated to unleash their entrepreneurial potential. Besides enticing skilled mothers, consequentially, companies could save resources on hiring costs since they could find suitable applicants quicker. That means that mothers would be valuable and irreplaceable while the diversified teams would have their own traits that could not be exactly copied by other organizations (mothers would strengthen corporate competitive advantages).

The business world as a whole is using cutting-edge technologies; thus, a new approach at the HR department (with emphasis on external learning partnerships) is necessary (Stachová et al., 2019). External learning providers could speed up and individualize the learning experience for all mothers coming back to work after a long time off, since these employees require to relearn their skills and catch up with updates to their work environment. Techniques for employee development could vary (e.g., external mentorship programs). However, most modern companies choose employee-driven courses and programs, where a worker has a full control of course selection (Dachner et al., 2021). Maternity leave costs a lot to employers both directly and indirectly. Using that time to further develop their workforce could create a competitive advantage.

Corporate social responsibility (CSR) is another area in which competitive advantages could be initiated. CSR is an increasingly more significant part of employer's branding from both the company's and candidate's perspectives (Carlini et al., 2019). Organizations could develop and publicize some elements of their employer's branding strategy to specifically attract female talents. Some of these partnership-based bonuses could include private healthcare insurance with a focus on childcare, mobile applications that assist during early parenthood or workspaces designed for pregnant

women. In addition to helping with talent acquisition, these additional bonuses could increase job satisfaction and lower job stress among existing employees. The quantitative research suggests that these changes would have a positive effect on turnover intention among employees (Yukongdi & Shrestha, 2020). Ultimately, there are two HR competitive advantages that could be created using partner bonus packages: more efficient talent acquisition and better employee retention rate. Moreover, there are more niche opportunities that could be embraced via strategic partnerships. For example, Willis-Knighton Health System saw an opportunity outside traditional brand marketing by designing and distributing their iconic branded teddy bear mascot to all mothers who gave birth to a baby at their institution (Elrod & Fortenberry, 2018). This strategy could be used by turning all company mothers into brand ambassadors and advocates, while corporate ambassadors can often be more effective at enhancing brand awareness and reputation than traditional corporate communication strategies (Wæraas & Dahle, 2020), while liaising it to a business model and market characteristics (Rodríguez-Vilá's et al., 2024)

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY: ASSUMPTIONS AND EFFECTS ON BUSINESS

Driven by the aim to examine the link between socio-economic environment, organizational culture, family status, income, entrepreneurship support systems, gender equality, and mothers' perception on their career (along with entrepreneurial and intrapreneurial aspirations), the triangulation methodology has been applied. The main topic of this paper has been explored from three different perspectives: the global context and similar studies, quantitative comparative research to examine Lithuanian mothers' perceptions, semi-structured interviews with experts of corporations willing to reshape the business environment for maternal entrepreneurship, innovation, and intrapreneurship, along with competitive advantages that could be

enhanced by mother entrepreneurs and intrapreneurs.

According to Meyer (2018), the research subject is not yet fully understood, thus assumptions and implications are particularly valuable in the academic world. The qualitative research helps find questions that have not been explored before, the literature review proposes specific niche topics, related to business innovation and entrepreneurship/ intrapreneurship during motherhood, while the quantitative research is aimed to understand and further test mothers' career choices, behaviour, and entrepreneurial aspirations within the geographical boundaries of Lithuania.

3.1. Quantitative Research

Non-probability sampling method was chosen since there was no possibility to ensure an equal chance of participation of all Lithuanian mothers due to geographical, cost, and time reasons. According to large population formula with 95% confidence level (maximum error of 2,5%), 292 respondents were required. The sample with 95% confidence level has a lowered error margin of 2,35%. In the end, 359 answers were collected and 24 of them were dismissed to leave only qualifying responses. Descriptive statistics was used to evaluate any statistical differences between variables, inferential tests (for instance, ANOVA) were used to compare the formulated motivations and conditions or to identify statistically significant correlations, and lastly, a couple of regressions were formulated. A narrower population of Lithuanian mothers who are pregnant or with children between 0 and 2 years old has been chosen for more statistical significance when calculating results, therefore, extra 5 answers were removed leaving 330 qualifying answers.

For the quantitative research 7 hypotheses were formulated (Table 1) and grouped into two sections based on the main topics: mother entrepreneurship and mother intrapreneurship. The null hypothesis for each assumption is that there is no effect between the factor and mother's perspective on entrepreneurship or intrapreneurship.

Table 1: Hypotheses for Quantitative Research.

Topic	Hypothesis	Sources
Mother Entrepreneurship	H1: Higher number of working mothers from the service sector (compared to other sectors) have entrepreneurial aspirations.	Consumer-oriented services on average are the most popular choices among new startup founders (GEM, 2022).
	H2: The key mothers' career motive is aspiration to earn more money.	Research conducted in 25 countries throughout 6 years found that monetary reward is one of the key factors that encourages women to start international companies (Jafari-Sadeghi et al., 2021).

	H3: Lack of time is one of the most relevant problems that mothers encounter when working in an organization.	Birth induces time pressure, but from the 2nd birth mothers start feeling its effects more (Ruppanner et al., 2018)
	H4: Women who have 2 or more children feel having insufficient time for themselves and would appreciate work flexibility more than women with 1 child.	
Mother Intrapreneurship	H5: The more ensured gender equality, corporate social responsibility (CSR), implementation of ethical and moral values-based philosophy, alongside innovative climate, are in an organization, the more likely it will lead to a higher number of mothers generating new ideas and developing their ventures.	Innovation study in 20 countries shows that funding CSR also promotes corporate innovation (Chkir et al., 2021).
	H6: Mothers representing companies with a better work life balance are more likely to initiate their innovation activities, being optimistic and feeling psychological comfort.	Based on the research in service innovation, there is a profound positive effect of work-life balance in service innovation (Junior et al., 2021)
	H7: A supportive, equal, and encouraging innovation environment (with sufficient time dedicated to creative activities) in an organization has a positive effect on mothers' will to participate in intrapreneurial ventures.	Based on the quantitative research, the more attention is paid to equality and work-life balance, the higher quality results are achieved in organizational innovation (Youngwook et al., 2021).

Source: created by authors based on GEM (2022), Jafari-Sadeghi et al. (2021), Ruppanner et al. (2018), Chkir et al. (2021), Junior et al. (2021), Youngwook et al. (2021).

3.2. Qualitative Research

The qualitative research was oriented to Lithuanian companies operating domestically or internationally to evaluate work conditions and career opportunities (specifically for mothers and more generally women and employees despite their gender). The main purpose is to get insight into intrapreneurial prospects for women and mothers and reveal whether organizations in Lithuania are open to entrepreneurship (whether it is inside or outside a company). Given that intrapreneurship is still being a rather new concept in practice and consequently not a thoroughly discussed topic, this research is of significant value to both scholars and organizational entities facing the challenge of unleashing potential of entrepreneurial women. To gather in-depth qualitative perceptions and test the

assumptions, the semi-structured interviews with 8 experts were conducted. Experts were required to have at least 3 years of managerial and extensive entrepreneurial experiences (to be able to gain insights from younger specialists, while ensuring that all representatives have a sufficient understanding of processes at their current companies). Moreover, it was agreed to respect equal representation of expert categories in terms of gender to have more variance in respondents and ensure that both gender representatives may express their perceptions. At the same time, a significant attention was paid to organizations with various percentages of women employees in total headcount and in leadership teams. Finally, it was focused on sectors, covering finance, governmental, social, education, and commercial categories, which is in line with the National Experts Survey methodology, applied by GEM Consortium (2022). The interviewed companies were coded to look into any potential discrepancies stemming from manager characteristics, as well as based on their gender, generation, and entrepreneurial experiences (see the Table 2 and 3).

Table 2: Organizational Characteristics.

Manager	Internationality n - national i - international	Sector a - multiple b - services c - trade d - public sector e - education	Employee count a - 1-20 b - 21-100 c - 101-500 d - 501+	Percentage of women employees a - [0-20] % b - (20-40) % c - (40-60) % d - (60-80) % e - (80-100) %	Percentage of women leaders a - [0-20] %, b - (20-40) % c - (40-60) % d - (60-80) % e - (80-100) %	Full code
1	n	b	b	B	a	nbbba
2	n	e	c	B	e	nebbe
3	n	c	a	D	d	ncadd
4	i	a	d	C	b	iadcb
5	n	b	a	D	d	nbadd
6	n	d	b	E	a	ndbea
7	n	a	c	C	c	naccb
8	n	d	b	E	d	ndbed

Source: created by authors (2025).

Table 3: Experts' Characteristics.

Manager	Gender x - female y - male	Generation x y z	Experience in entrepreneurship or intrapreneurship x - yes y - no	Full code
1	y	y	x	yyx
2	x	x	x	xxx
3	x	z	y	xzy
4	x	y	y	xyy
5	y	z	x	yzx
6	y	y	y	yyy
7	x	y	x	xyx
8	x	x	y	xyy

Source: created by authors (2025).

In total 7 assumptions were formulated. All were created in accordance with the literature review. The first theoretical framework is inspired by empathy, relating to similar pain points and partly the affinity bias where people tend to favour people alike them (Oberai & Anand, 2018). In the intrapreneurial world it can be expressed as "When the access to communication with managers is more frequent and interactive (an expert has more experience in suggesting and implementing new ideas), an expert knows the context of entrepreneurial employees better and is more likely to help them."

The second perception stems from the research on how age affects intrapreneurship with findings that older members can use their know-how, being able to control resources and aid using that to fulfil their ideas (Hador & Klein, 2019) or in regard to the topic of this research: "Different generation managers' opinions on women/mother intrapreneurship opportunities are different: y and z generation managers see more possibilities." The third conceptual dimension: "Companies that are more open to intrapreneurship are more likely to hire employees, based on their competencies rather than personal traits (such as gender, age, nationality, and etc.)." mostly relates to discrimination risk mitigation and the importance of gender equality and mutual respect, calling for a continuous, respectful, kind, and interactive dialogue between men and women.

Another characteristic influencing intrapreneurship besides organizational culture and inclusion is openness to technology. It is represented in the subsequent conceptual framework condition stating that "Companies highlighting technology more are also inclined to introduce more financial initiatives to support them and encourage synergy through cooperation." Thus, the following conception relates more to women and mothers: "Companies that have more women managers better understand entrepreneurial mother problems," which is explained by women managers being able

to recognize challenges faced by mothers better due to similar experiences. The last assumption is as follows: "Bigger companies are more favouring the initiatives of entrepreneurial employees because they have more experience and resources to unleash the strategic partnerships with ventures created by former/ present employees."

Given that Lithuania is a feminine culture with a score of 19 on the masculinity dimension (Hofstede Insights, 2021), it suggests that support should be attainable to mothers, and it raises expectations that the hypotheses and theoretical framework conditions might be confirmed and that entrepreneurial and intrapreneurial grounds in Lithuania are well-developed and sufficient.

4. RESEARCH RESULTS

4.1. Quantitative research results

Starting the research results interpretation from the potential business perspective, it is interesting to note that 73,6% of women were eager to establish a company; However, only 50,3% had the intention to do so. No statistically significant difference was found depending on gross income nor on the willingness to develop a business. An identical situation is seen with age group and sectors. A statistically equal portion of pregnant and not pregnant women were willing to develop a business; However, it was found that more pregnant women (69,2%) in comparison to not currently pregnant women (48,7%) are planning to follow an entrepreneurial route ($\chi^2(1) = 4,045$; $p = 0,044$). A somewhat similar situation concerns the wish to create a business based on having children: statistically fewer women (48,9%) who have children intend to establish a company ($\chi^2(1) = 4,049$; $p = 0,036$), compared to women without children (73,7%). From the intrapreneurial perspective, mothers who feel more supported and encouraged by leaders in creating new products, might stay more loyal, creative, and productive.

While examining statistical disparities between monthly income, based on age, Kruskal-Wallis ($\chi^2(3) = 30,870$; $p < 0,001$) suggested that there were differences between the age groups, which was confirmed by Mann-Whitney tests: women belonging to older age groups were more likely to choose a higher earning category, compared to younger ones. No statistical significance was discovered when evaluating monthly income depending on work sector; However, when comparing income categorized by marital status (Kruskal-Wallis $\chi^2(3) = 10,638$, $p = 0,014$), it was discovered that married mothers (MR = 151,16) were likelier to select a higher-earning category than engaged ones (MR = 110,50) MW U = 2850, Z = -2,523, $p = 0,012$. It might be related to Lithuania's phenomenon of married couples having more income equality in comparison to not married couples or individuals with respectively larger income discrepancies (Černiauskas *et al.*, 2021), which could explain why married mothers earn more. Furthermore, the number of children did not differ among various income groups, but it is logically related to the age categories.

While examining motives for choosing an entrepreneurial, intrapreneurial, or employment career via assessment of factors within multiple independent samples on the interval scale, the means were compared through repeated measures ANOVA. According to Bonferroni test, it was determined that two motives are the most important when it comes to choosing a career: the possibility to earn more money (M = 4,71) – it is more important than the ability to work from home (M = 4,31; $p < 0,001$) or to express one's creativity (M = 4,14; $p < 0,001$), having a more flexible work schedule (M=4,55; $p < 0,001$), being independent from manager (M=4,14; $p < 0,001$) and adding value to society (M=4,28; $p < 0,001$). This finding proves that the hypothesis 2 regarding a higher income being the leading factor for Lithuanian mothers in making career choices is correct. The second most relevant motive is work flexibility which is more significant than working from home, creativity expression, independence from a manager, and value added to society, since all the comparisons between these career considerations have a statistically significant difference ($p < 0,01$).

When analysing statements related to corporate social responsibility and employee inclusion in the workplace due to multiple variables being independent from one another and all being interval scale, repeated measures ANOVA was used again. Through the test it was found that there were no

statistically significant conditions that would be evaluated better than others; However, there is one point that statistically is viewed as more insufficient than other conditions: Greenhouse-Geisser F (4,457) = 21,042, $p < 0,001$. Based on Bonferroni test results women feel that they do not have enough work life balance since the mean for statement "I have enough time for myself" (M = 2,78) is statistically lower than "There is no discrimination in the workplace" (M = 3,48; $p < 0,001$), "Equal career opportunities" (M = 3,44; $p < 0,001$), "Opportunities to develop business ideas within the company" (M = 3,55; $p < 0,001$), "Help and support being attainable" (M = 3,40; $p < 0,001$) or "The employer providing enough assistance and sustenance" (M = 3,22; $p < 0,001$). This is in line with the findings from the theory and simultaneously it allows to confirm the hypothesis 3, which claims that the lack of time is the most pertinent problem for mothers in their workplaces.

Notwithstanding the identified significant difference, while interpreting entrepreneurial conditions (Greenhouse-Geisser F (5,718) = 24,843, $p < 0,001$), when going through pairwise comparisons of the statements, no discrepancies were found that would have been evaluated statistically differently from other statements. However, since the disparity through Greenhouse-Geisser was detected, it was decided to more ingeniously analyse some conditions which were viewed as significantly better or worse evaluated than a certain number of other work climate statements. Starting with the better evaluated ones according to the applied Bonferroni test, the first would be "Company is actively creating an environment where employees are not afraid to express their opinions" (M = 3,20). It was statistically more sufficient than 6 other statements and did not differ only from the statement that employees being encouraged to develop their own ideas (M = 3,07; $p = 0,869$), as well as that employees' initiatives are valued (M = 3,12; $p = 1,000$).

Regarding the least satisfactory conditions, the first would be the lack of employees receiving access to resources to generate and evolve their ideas (M = 2,56). It is more challenging than 6 statements. Two conditions that it does not differ significantly from are the existence of a certain department or person for generating and implementing ideas ($p = 0,559$) and the clarity of the process of creating them ($p = 0,220$). Process being unclear is the second circumstance interpreted as more deficient since it is statistically worse evaluated than 5 other statements. Lastly, to check whether the hypothesis 4 was correct, it was decided to execute 2 more one-way ANOVA tests comparing the evaluations of work schedule

flexibility career motive and amount of time for oneself depending on the number of children: first one with 3 children number categories and the second test with 2 groups. 2 tests were conducted since categories "2" and "3 or more" were transformed into joint "2 or more" for more reliable results. However, neither of them showed any statistical significance. Such results suggest that there is no difference between women who have or do not have sufficient time and mothers who would or would not wish to have more worktime elasticity depending on their number of children. Therefore, hypothesis 4 can be rejected.

4.2. Correlation and regression analysis

To evaluate relationships between various career motives or workplace conditions, a correlation analysis was performed. Out of 231 correlations only 57 have a correlation coefficient of 0,4 or more and could be deemed meaningful. To begin with correlations within the section of career aspirations, Pearson Correlation was executed, along with two-tailed tests used to provide more precise and reliable results (Birkett, 2021). The analysis uncovered that with 95% confidence level, there are 1 strong and 8 medium positive correlations. A strong liaison was identified between the willingness to earn more and have a more flexible schedule $r = 0,615$, $p < 0,001$. Regarding the medium correlations, they were detected between work flexibility and expressing creativity $r = 0,404$, work from home and flexible work schedule $r = 0,546$, ingenuity expression and independence from manager $r = 0,466$, which also correlated with work time flexibility $r = 0,525$ and ability to earn a higher salary $r = 0,468$. The last three medium positive relationships were found amid value added to society and unleashing creativity potential $r = 0,469$, autonomous work without a manager ($r = 0,485$) and possibility to gain more income ($r = 0,488$). The statistical significance of all these correlations was $p < 0,001$.

Within the section of general organizational conditions, only two medium positive correlations were identified: between equal career possibilities and equal business development within a company opportunity ($r = 0,533$), $p < 60 0,001$. The second medium liaison was between help and support being attainable in an organization and the employer providing support for mothers ($r = 0,545$, $p < 0,001$). Regarding intrapreneurial conditions in mothers' workplaces, 23 strong and 11 medium correlations were discovered, all with significance of $p < 0,001$. The statement with the most statistically significant strong correlations was "Employee initiatives are

valued" since it had 7 firm positive correlations. On the other hand, fewest liaisons were found with the statement "There is a clear department and/or person responsible for idea generation and development" since it had mostly weak or medium correlations and only one strong liaisons with the process of idea generation and development (being clear $r = 0,798$, $p < 0,001$).

To examine the hypotheses 5, 6, and 7, correlations, related to general and intrapreneurial conditions, were executed. For that, another variable "Intrapreneurial conditions" reflected the mean of sufficiency of all intrapreneurship related statements for each respondent; thus, instead of comparing only separate climate evaluations, the overall satisfaction was correlated as well. Since the 5th hypothesis mostly focuses on equality and moral values assurance in the workplace surroundings, statements (a. I have not experienced discrimination in the workplace, b. Men and women have equal career opportunities, c. Men and women have the same opportunities to develop business idea(s) within a company) were correlated. Even though, all analyses identified statistically significant connections, they all were weak or very weak positive correlations, e.g., the more men and women have equal opportunities to develop a business inside their company, the more likely that employees are encouraged by an employer to create and implement those ideas $r = 0,268$, $p < 0,001$. That could mean that gender equality is not yet associated with intrapreneurship in Lithuania. Overall, the 5th hypothesis is neither rejected nor accepted yet.

While delving in liaisons between factors, related to the 6th hypothesis, the relation between work life balance and intrapreneurial activities, with the emphasis on the statement "I have enough time for myself", was examined. In this case, only 5 out of 9 correlations were deemed statistically significant and even those were very weak positive connections. The same was seen regarding "sufficient time". Therefore, due to insufficient evidence, the hypothesis 6 is rejected. Lastly, for the hypothesis 7, statements concerning organizational support (e. "Help and support is available in my organization" and f. "My employer provides support for mothers") were correlated with separate and joined evaluations of the intrapreneurial conditions. In this circumstance, mostly medium positive connections have been identified with several others being weak positive relations. The medium correlations are between both general condition statements and employees being encouraged to create their own ideas ($r = 0,441$, $r = 0,463$, with e. and f. respectively).

The liaisons with “Those ideas being usually implemented” ($r = 0,418$, $r = 0,420$), “Environment enabling staff to freely share their opinions” ($r = 0,515$, $r = 0,517$), “The employer having enough tools to manage risks” ($r = 0,463$, $r = 0,420$), “Worker initiatives being valued” ($r = 0,431$, $r = 0,507$), “Respondents’ ideas being heard and appreciated too” ($r = 0,418$, $r = 0,495$) were marked by statistically significant ($p < 0,001$) connections. The joined conditions also suggest medium positive correlations with the statement that support being attainable (e.) $r = 0,498$, $p < 0,001$ and provided to mothers (f.) $r = 0,523$, $p < 0,001$. Consequentially, the hypothesis that supportive and encouraging innovation setting in the workplace may relate to mothers’ interest in intrapreneurship and opportunities to participate in intrapreneurial projects is partly confirmed.

Based on the results of the correlation analysis several regressions have been modelled to further investigate the relationship between the variables. Statistical significance in both cases was determined using the p-value for the overall F-test. There is a statistically significant simple linear regression between mothers’ opinion that employees are encouraged to create and develop their own ideas and the opinion that innovative ideas from employees are usually implemented in the organization. The latter being an independent variable which means that when an organization increases their idea implementation frequency it also should increase the employee’s perceived appreciation and innovation encouragement. Another statistically significant simple linear regression has been found using the independent variable statement as the organization has sufficient risk management tools to ensure the success of ideas and a dependent variable as innovative ideas from employees are usually implemented in the organization. Thus, better risk management tools provided to employees would increase the total number of implemented intrapreneurial ideas.

Therefore, correlations and regressions analysis reveals, that respondents who think that intrapreneurial idea generation and development processes are clearly defined in their company tend to also believe that employees are encouraged to develop their ideas, innovative ideas are usually commercialized, there is efficient risk management mechanism, employees’ ideas are valued and there is a clear department or person responsible for new venture development. The implication, that there is a strong correlation of 0,748 between respondents who think that their company values and respects opinions, expressed by employees, and those who

think that ideas initiated by employees are commercialized successfully within their company is of significant value. There is also a linear statistically significant regression between these two variables found. Respondents who expressed that their company has clearly defined processes of new ideas generation and development also believe that there is a clearly specified department or a person responsible for this process and this relationship makes up another strong positive correlation of 0,798. The organizational support has the most correlations with the intrapreneurial environment in comparison to equality and morals in the workplace or time sufficiency (supportive organizations are likelier to have well developed intrapreneurial grounds).

4.3. Qualitative research results

Qualitative research on strengthening corporate competitive advantages through intrapreneurship among mothers is anchored in 7 theoretical framework dimensions, explored in the methodology section. In regard to the conceptual framework condition “When experts have more experience in introducing and implementing their business ideas, they know the context of entrepreneurial employees better and are more likely to help them.”, the experts’ interviews results do not confirm that entrepreneurship experience influences a manager’ ability and willingness to help entrepreneurial employees: the evaluated statements regarding innovation and support for entrepreneurial employees reveal that both, managers with and without entrepreneurial experience have a consensus on 6 out 7 statements with an average evaluation difference of $\leq 1,5$. Managers with no entrepreneurship experience represent companies that are more inclined to offer financial support for employees with intrapreneurial ideas with their average evaluation score of 4,75, as opposed to managers with entrepreneurial experience (2,75). This could mean that companies that are willing to financially support intrapreneurial activities of their employees, are more prone to hiring people with no entrepreneurship experience for managerial roles and reshaping them to a standard expert in the first year of managers’ careers. Overall, all managers, with or without entrepreneurship experience, highly evaluated statements regarding providing opportunities to start a business while working at a company, supporting an employee in developing/ enhancing a product, pursuing strategic partnerships with their ex-employees, ensuring sufficient educational material, leading to better

market understanding, and helping women to manage business risks (averages answers ranging from 6,75 to 8 out of 10). The statements regarding usage of modern technology in identifying entrepreneurial women and providing financial support for employees' intrapreneurial activities were considered less important (means of 2,75 and 4,75).

While tackling the theoretical framework condition "Different generation managers' opinions on women/ mother intrapreneurship opportunities are different: y and z generation managers see more possibilities", the responses reveal that higher evaluations were related to numerous and often greater possibilities for entrepreneurial or intrapreneurial mothers or employees in general. Gen Z managers did evaluate 4 out of the 7 statements the highest (reaching values of 8 or 9), while the highest evaluation score accorded by Gen X managers reaches the mark of 5,5. To validate the conceptual framework dimension "Companies highlighting technology more are also inclined to introduce more financial initiatives to support them and encourage synergy through cooperation", 4 out of 7 managers evaluated statements (implementation of modern technology for identifying entrepreneurial women; pursuing strategic partnerships with their ex-employees; collaboration helping women to manage business risks, and providing financial support for employees' intrapreneurial activities) - of greater significance. "ndbed" evaluated their implemented modern technology tools as highly important with a score of 9; "necbe" and "ndbea" gave the first statement a score of 5, "nacc" - 6, while remaining companies do not or seldom use modern technologies for identifying entrepreneurial women with their allocated scores not exceeding 2. The companies that accentuate technological importance ("nacc" and "ndbed") were, indeed, evaluated by their managers as the most inclined to offer financial support for intrapreneurial ideas - assessed as 7 out of 10. Ndbea's manager, who evaluated their technology usage at the mark of 5, assessed the willingness to provide financial support with a score of 6. On the other hand, "necbe", who also allocated 5 for technology use, evaluated their inclination to provide financial aid much lower - with a score of 2.

The insights deriving from two statements regarding partnerships and guidance through collaborations elucidate that half of the interviewed companies evaluated both statements highly - allocated scores ranging from 6 to 8. However, the highest given scores for both statements came from the managers of the companies that do not highlight

the importance of modern technology - 10 for strategic partnerships with ex-employees from the company "ncadd" and 9 for collaborations helping women with risk management from companies "nbbba" and "nbadd". To conclude, companies highlighting the role of modern technologies for identifying entrepreneurial women are more inclined to also provide financial aid and encourage cooperation, while companies that do not use the modern technology and do not offer any financial support are more willing to inspire synergy through strategic collaborations.

While delving in the theoretical framework condition "Companies that have more women managers understand entrepreneurial mother problems better", the companies with the highest percentage of women in managerial roles are "ndbed", "nbadd", "ncadd", and "necbe" with their female managers representing 65%, 67%, 75%, and 90% of the managerial staff, respectively. Reviewing the challenges faced by returning mothers, all experts accentuated adapting to new staff members, lack of current target market and other job-related information, lacking skills set, not competitive salaries, lower resistance to workloads, and the need for extra day-offs. When asked about tools/initiatives used to encourage mothers to return after their maternity leave, all managers (except "yzx") indicated maintaining the positions for mothers to return without worrying about losing their income source. Some also added having pre-return meetings with the mothers to ensure a smooth transition, while discussing workload scheduling limitations.

Regarding the conceptual framework condition "Companies that are more open to intrapreneurship are more likely to hire employees based on their competencies rather than personal traits (gender, age, nationality and so on).", all analysed companies were stated to be open to intrapreneurship. Evaluating hiring practices, it is clear that all of them perceive the capacity and experience of candidates as the most important criteria in the hiring process. When asked about ways their companies ensured gender equality in the workplace, managers cited the equal rights implemented by the board, hiring and training processes conducted to everybody equally, opportunities provided according to the achievements and determination of an employee, unbiased salaries, unified language used in job advertisements, being awarded for paying fair salaries, decisions being made by the majority vote, and prioritizing qualitative work output and respect among colleagues. It is difficult to conclude if any of them can be considered as "more likely to" deem

competency above personal traits for their applicants than others. Regarding the statement that “Mother entrepreneurial conditions may be ensured only when there is a continuous, respectful, kind, and interactive dialogue between men and women”, all interviewed companies hire accordingly to candidates’ competencies, not personal traits, accompanied by the fact that none of the managers indicated any cases of gender inequality at their represented companies (assuming they were completely truthful in their answers). It is evident that respectful and interactive communication between genders does ensure a more open space for entrepreneurial and intrapreneurial ventures.

To explore the theoretical framework dimension “Bigger companies are more favouring the initiatives of entrepreneurial employees (including the cases of demerging from a company via new entrepreneurship projects) because they have more experience and resources to establish strategic partnerships with the ventures created by the former/ present employees”, the allocated scores for the statements (implementation of modern technology for identifying entrepreneurial women; ensuring sufficient educational material for better market understanding, and providing financial support for employees) intrapreneurial ventures were categorized according to a company size metric. It is apparent, that among the 8 companies, openness to entrepreneurial activity among employees does rise in tandem with the growing company size. Openness to entrepreneurial ideas of companies with their employee counts of 1-20, 21-100, and 101-500 was evaluated with the score averages of 5,66, 6,33, and 7,5, respectively. However, the manager of the company with the largest headcount out of all companies – of over 20 thousand (“iadc”) – evaluated their company’s entrepreneurial climate with a score average of 5,66. The manager indicated that many strategic partnerships are not allowed; therefore, encouraging entrepreneurship would not bring many benefits to the organization, and instead, it is better to retain talented employees.

In conclusion, 2 out of the 7 theoretical framework conditions were confirmed, 2 were partly confirmed and 3 were rejected. Lithuanian companies prioritize ensuring equal opportunities to all employees and providing support to returning mothers. Nurturing entrepreneurial and intrapreneurial efforts becomes more important as the companies grow in size, with Gen Z managers more inclined to support employee ventures. Companies highlighting technological importance, while identifying entrepreneurial women, are also more willing to support them

financially.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The subdomain terms maternal entrepreneurship and intrapreneurship are relatively new and academically undeveloped. A mompreneur could be defined as a mother who made a career pivot decision into intrapreneurship or entrepreneurship during her experience of motherhood. Various factors may encourage or hinder entrepreneurship or intrapreneurship, ranging from financial gain, technology, and innovation to psychological, social, and environmental factors. It has also been found that in feminine cultures mothers are likelier to receive affirmation and support for participating in entrepreneurial activities, compared to masculine cultures.

The organizational environment plays a vital role on the level of mompreneurship within a company. According to the best practices, a systematic support and risk mitigation are the two best strategies that can help encourage maternal intrapreneurship. Management (in particular, the HR department) is responsible for implementation and consistent monitoring of these strategies. Mothers’ qualities, such as creativity, resilience, and skills (for instance, time management or networking), were analysed and established to be able to lead to sustainable competitive advantages, such as increased innovation, more diverse organizational culture, and corporate social responsibility.

Based on quantitative research, it has been observed that pregnant women have more entrepreneurial intentions than mothers. Additional findings show that the key drivers for mothers when choosing a career are the ability to increase their income and have more flexible work time arrangements: they wish to have more work-life balance. Even though companies encourage employees to express their ideas, workers lack access to resources to commercialize their ideas.

Based on the qualitative research, companies tend to prioritize equal opportunities for their employees, while providing support to returning mothers. Encouraging entrepreneurial and intrapreneurial efforts becomes more essential as companies grow in size. Younger managers are more willing to support employee ventures in general. Companies highlighting the role of modern technology, while identifying entrepreneurial women, are also more inclined to provide a financial support.

In terms of further research, the context of both parents might enrich implications and recommendations. The connection between views on

corporate social responsibility and intrapreneurial conditions should be further explored. In addition to that, it is vital to expand this academic discussion to

other countries and regions, preferably using the triangulation methodology for easier comparisons and generalizations.

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